

Appendix: Runtime Change Issue in Google Play Top 100 Apps

1. Methodology

For each app, we start the app with a screen size of 1920x1080 and prepare the initial state for different types of apps. For instance, for apps with text boxes, we set the text boxes with textual contents. For apps with a selection list, we select an item different from the default one. For apps with a scroll bar, we change the scroll location of the scroll bar. After the preparation, the state of the app is denoted as State A. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change by resizing the screen to 540x960 and then changing it back. After the runtime configuration change, the state of the app is denoted as State B. We compare State B with State A to check whether there is a state loss.

2. Experimental Results

We present the specific experimental results for each app in the top 100 apps of the Google Play store. The runtime change issues are marked with red boxes.

1. **Amazon Prime Video.** First, we populate the username and password boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Amazon Prime Video. After the restart, the textual contents in the username and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 1.
2. **Filto.** First, we select a filter (i.e., the fourth filter) in the filter list. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Filto. After the restart, the selected filter is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 2.
3. **TikTok.** First, we populate the phone number box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to TikTok. After the restart, the numeric content in the phone number box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 3.
4. **Instagram.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Instagram.
5. **WhatsApp.** We do not find a runtime change issue with WhatsApp.
6. **Cash App.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Cash App.
7. **Deep Cleaner.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Deep Cleaner.
8. **ZOOM.** We do not find a runtime change issue with ZOOM.
9. **Disney+.** First, we scroll down the Privacy Policy to a location that is different from the original one. Then,

Figure 1: Amazon Prime Video. The textual contents in the username and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 2: Filto. The selected filter is lost after the restart.

- we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Disney+. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 4.
10. **Snapchat.** First, we populate the email and password boxes with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Snapchat. After the restart, the textual contents in the email and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 5.
11. **Amazon Shopping.** We do not find a runtime change

Figure 3: TikTok. The numeric content in the phone number box is lost after the restart.

Figure 5: Snapchat. The textual contents in the email and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 4: Disney+. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 6: Telegram. The numeric content in the phone number box is lost after the restart.

issue with Amazon Shopping.

12. **Telegram.** First, we populate the phone number box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Telegram. After the restart, the numeric content in the phone number box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 6.
13. **Tor Browser.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Tor Browser.
14. **Max Cleaner.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Max Cleaner.
15. **Messenger.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Messenger.
16. **Peacock TV.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Peacock TV.
17. **Walmart Shopping.** First, we scroll down the Con-

sumer Service to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Walmart Shopping. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 7.

18. **McDonald's.** We do not find a runtime change issue with McDonald's.
19. **Facebook.** First, we select a language (i.e., the second one) in the language list. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Facebook. After the restart, the language selection list is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 8.
20. **NewsBreak.** First, we populate the search box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime con-

Figure 7: Walmart Shopping. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 9: NewsBreak. The textual content in the search box is lost after the restart.

Figure 8: Facebook. The language selection list is lost after the restart.

Figure 10: QR & Barcode Scanner. The cursor of the zoom bar is reset to the initial position after the restart.

figuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to NewsBreak. After the restart, the textual content in the search box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 9.

21. **CapCut.** We do not find a runtime change issue with CapCut.
22. **QR & Barcode Scanner.** First, we drag the cursor of the zoom bar to a position that is different from the initial position. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to QR & Barcode Scanner. After the restart, the cursor of the zoom bar is reset to the initial position. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 10.
23. **Microsoft Teams.** First, we populate the user name, meeting ID, and meeting password boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime con-

figuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Microsoft Teams. After the restart, the textual contents in the user name, meeting ID, and meeting password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 11.

24. **Indeed Job Search.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Indeed Job Search.
25. **Tubi.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Tubi.
26. **SHEIN.** First, we select a cloth with a color (i.e., violet purple) that is different from the default one (i.e., maroon). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to SHEIN. After the restart, the selected color is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 11: Microsoft Teams. The textual contents in the user name, meeting ID, and meeting password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 12: SHEIN. The selected color is reset to the default one after the restart.

27. **TextNow.** First, we populate the email and password boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to TextNow. After the restart, the login page is lost. The contents in the email and password boxes of the login page are also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 13.
28. **Twitter.** First, we populate the user name box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Twitter. After the restart, the textual content in the user name box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 14.
29. **Wonder.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Wonder.

Figure 13: TextNow. The login page is lost after the restart.

Figure 14: Twitter. The textual content in the user name box is lost after the restart.

30. **Netflix.** First, we expand the FAQ list to a state that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Netflix. After the restart, the state of the FAQ list is reset to the initial one (i.e., unexpanded). The experimental result is shown in Fig. 15.
31. **All Document Reader.** First, we select a language (i.e., French) that is different from the default one (i.e., English). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to All Document Reader. After the restart, the selected language is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 16.
32. **Roku.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Roku.
33. **Pluto TV.** We do not find a runtime change issue with

Figure 15: Netflix. The state of the FAQ list (i.e., expanded) is reset to the initial one (i.e., unexpanded) after the restart.

Figure 16: All Document Reader. The selected language is reset to the default one after the restart.

Pluto TV.

34. **DoorDash.** First, we select a drop-off option (i.e., hand it to me) that is different from the default one (i.e., leave it at my door). We also populate the text box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to DoorDash. After the restart, the selected drop-off option is reset to the default one. The textual content in the text box is also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 17.
35. **Uber.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Uber.
36. **Discord.** First, we populate the phone number box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Discord. After the restart,

Figure 17: DoorDash. After the restart, the selected drop-off option is reset to the default one. The textual content in the text box is also lost.

Figure 18: Discord. The register page is lost after the restart.

the register page is lost. The numeric content in the phone number box of the register page is also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 18.

37. **Audible.** First, we populate the email and password boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Audible. After the restart, the contents in the email and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 19.
38. **Ticketmaster.** First, we select a ticket (i.e., Sec 217, Row 9) that is different from the default one (i.e., Sec 201, Row 1). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Ticketmaster. After the restart, the selected ticket is reset to the default one. The experimental

Figure 19: Audible. The contents in the email and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 21: Hulu. The textual content in the email box is lost after the restart.

Figure 20: Ticketmaster. The selected ticket is reset to the default one after the restart.

Figure 22: Orbot. The selected network bridge is reset to the default one after the restart.

- result is shown in Fig. 20.
39. **Life360.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Life360.
 40. **Hulu.** First, we populate the email box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Hulu. After the restart, the textual content in the email box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 21.
 41. **Orbot.** First, we select a network bridge (i.e., Custom Bridges) that is different from the default one (i.e., connect through community servers). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Orbot. After the restart, the selected network bridge is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 22.

42. **Move to iOS.** First, we scroll down the Terms and Conditions to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Move to iOS. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 23.
43. **Daily Diary.** First, we populate the text box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Daily Diary. After the restart, the textual content in the text box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 24.
44. **Yoshion.** First, we select a layout (i.e., the third layout in the second row) that is different from the default one (i.e., the first layout). Then, we conduct a run-

Figure 23: Move to iOS. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 25: Yoshion. The selected layout is reset to the default one after the restart.

Figure 24: Daily Diary. The textual content in the text box is lost after the restart.

Figure 26: Microsoft Authenticator. The textual content in the email box is lost after the restart.

time configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Yoshion. After the restart, the selected layout is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 25.

- 45. **Microsoft Authenticator.** First, we populate the email box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Microsoft Authenticator. After the restart, the textual content in the email box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 26.
- 46. **Power Cleaner.** First, we conduct a network optimization, which is finished with a report page. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Power Cleaner. After the restart, the network optimization report page is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 27.

- 47. **Samsung Smart Switch Mobile.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Samsung Smart Switch Mobile.
- 48. **Alibaba.com.** First, we select an apparel category (i.e., Men's Clothing) that is different from the default one (i.e., Baby Clothing). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Alibaba.com. After the restart, the selected apparel category is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 28.
- 49. **Reddit.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Reddit.
- 50. **Paramount+.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Paramount+.
- 51. **Lyft.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Lyft.
- 52. **Pinterest.** First, we populate the email and password

Figure 27: Power Cleaner. The network optimization report page is lost after the restart.

Figure 29: Pinterest. The contents in the email and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 28: Alibaba.com. The selected apparel category is reset to the default one after the restart.

Figure 30: BeReal. The textual content in the user name box is lost after the restart.

boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Pinterest. After the restart, the contents in the email and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 29.

53. **OfferUp.** We do not find a runtime change issue with OfferUp.
54. **BeReal.** First, we populate the user name box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to BeReal. After the restart, the textual content in the user name box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 30.
55. **Uber Eats.** First, we populate the phone number box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration

change causes a restart to Uber Eats. After the restart, the login page is lost. The numeric content in the phone number box of the login page is also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 31.

56. **Fetch Rewards.** First, we scroll down the Privacy Policy to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Fetch Rewards. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 32.
57. **Haircut Prank.** First, we drag the cursor of the volume bar to a position that is different from the initial position. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Haircut Prank. After the restart, the cursor

Figure 31: Uber Eats. The login page is lost after the restart.

Figure 33: Haircut Prank. The cursor of the volume bar is reset to the initial position After the restart.

Figure 32: Fetch Rewards. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 34: My Bath & Body Works. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

of the volume bar is reset to the initial position. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 33.

58. **My Bath & Body Works.** First, we scroll down the Privacy Policy to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to My Bath & Body Works. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 34.
59. **Wholee.** First, we select a country (i.e., United States) that is different from the default one (i.e., United Kingdom). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Wholee. After the restart, the selected country is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 35.

60. **Ultra Cleaner.** First, we conduct a junk file scan, which is finished with a junk file count. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Ultra Cleaner. After the restart, the junk file count is reset. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 36.
61. **eBay.** We do not find a runtime change issue with eBay.
62. **FacebookLite.** First, we populate the email and password boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Facebook Lite. After the restart, the contents in the email and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 37.
63. **Adidas.** First, we scroll down the product list to a lo-

Figure 35: Wholee. The selected country is reset to the default one after the restart.

Figure 37: Facebook Lite. The contents in the email and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 36: Ultra Cleaner. The junk file count is reset after the restart.

Figure 38: Adidas. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

cation that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Adidas. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 38.

64. **Duolingo.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Duolingo.
65. **Bravo Cleaner.** First, we conduct a junk file scan, which is finished with a junk file report page. We cancel these default selected files. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Bravo Cleaner. After the restart, the junk file report page is reset. The unselected files are reset to the selected state. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 39.
66. **Cast For Chrome.** First, we select a payment method

(i.e., Onetime Payment) that is different from the default one (i.e., Get 3 Days Free Trial). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Cast For Chrome. After the restart, the selected payment method is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 40.

67. **Waze.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Waze.
68. **Ultrasurf.** First, we select a proxy that is different from the default one. We populate the proxy address, port, username, and password with text. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Ultrasurf. After the restart, the selected proxy is reset to the default one. The contents of the proxy register page are also

Figure 39: Bravo Cleaner. After the restart, the junk file report page is reset. The unselected files are reset to the selected state.

Figure 40: Cast For Chrome. The selected payment method is reset to the default one after the restart.

lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 41.

69. **Pet Diary.** First, we scroll down the Privacy Policy to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Pet Diary. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 42.
70. **King James Bible.** First, we populate the search box with the textual content and select several search ranges (i.e., Samuel, Ezra, Psalms, and Ecclesiastes). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to King James Bible. After the restart, the selected search ranges are lost. The experimental result is shown in

Figure 41: Ultrasurf. After the restart, the selected proxy is reset to the default one. The contents of the proxy register page are also lost.

Figure 42: Pet Diary. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Fig. 43.

71. **Email Home.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Email Home.
72. **Capital One.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Capital One.
73. **Plex.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Plex.
74. **Doordash Dasher.** First, we populate the ZIP code box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Doordash Dasher. After the restart, the textual content in the ZIP code box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 44.
75. **Shop.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Shop.
76. **Expedia.** First, we populate the email and password

Figure 43: King James Bible. The selected search ranges are lost after the restart.

Figure 45: Expedia. The contents in the email and password boxes are lost after the restart.

Figure 44: Doordash Dasher. The textual content in the ZIP code box is lost after the restart.

Figure 46: ESPN. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

- boxes with the textual contents. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Expedia. After the restart, the contents in the email and password boxes are lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 45.
77. **ESPN.** First, we scroll down the Score List to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to ESPN. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 46.
 78. **Pandora.** We do not find a runtime configuration issue with Pandora.
 79. **Picsart.** First, we scroll down the Lens Flare List to a location that is different from the original one. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The

- runtime configuration change causes a restart to Picsart. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 47.
80. **File Recovery.** First, we conduct a photo scan, which is finished with a report page and a photo count. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to File Recovery. After the restart, the report page and the photo count are reset. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 48.
 81. **Callapp.** First, we select a country (i.e., United States) that is different from the default one (i.e., India). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Callapp. After the restart, the selected country is reset to the default one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 49.

Figure 47: Picsart. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 49: Callapp. The selected country is reset to the default one after the restart.

Figure 48: File Recovery. The report page and the photo count are reset after the restart.

Figure 50: Tinder. The numeric content in the phone number box is lost after the restart.

82. **Tinder.** First, we populate the phone number box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Tinder. After the restart, the numeric content in the phone number box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 50.
83. **Etsy.** First, we populate the email box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Etsy. After the restart, the textual content in the email box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 51.
84. **SiriusXM.** We do not find a runtime change issue with SiriusXM.
85. **AliExpress.** First, we scroll down the country list to a location that is different from the original one. Then,

- we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to AliExpress. After the restart, the scroll location is reset to the initial one. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 52.
86. **NFL.** We do not find a runtime change issue with NFL.
87. **Adobe.** First, we populate the email box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Adobe. After the restart, the textual content in the email box is lost. The background picture is also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 53.
88. **KJV Bible.** First, we open the quiz page and wait for the timer to change to a value (i.e., 7) that is different from the original one (i.e., 24). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configura-

Figure 51: Etsy. The textual content in the email box is lost after the restart.

Figure 53: Adobe. After the restart, the textual content in the email box is lost. The background picture is also lost.

Figure 52: AliExpress. The scroll location is reset to the initial one after the restart.

Figure 54: KJV Bible. The timer is reset and counts down from 24 again after the restart.

tion change causes a restart to KJV Bible. After the restart, the timer is reset and counts down from 24 again. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 54.

89. **The Home Depot.** First, we select a store location (i.e., Cascade). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to The Home Depot. After the restart, the selected store location is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 55.
90. **TacoBell.** First, we populate the ZIP code with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to TacoBell. After the restart, the numeric content in the ZIP code box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 56.
91. **Uber Driver.** First, we populate the phone number

box with the numeric content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Uber Driver. After the restart, the numeric content in the phone number box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 57.

92. **Booking.com.** First, we populate the destination search box with the textual content. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Booking.com. After the restart, the textual content in the destination search box is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 58.
93. **CC FileManager.** First, we open the Storage page and move to a directory (i.e., Internal Storage/Android) that is different from the original one (i.e., Internal Storage). Then, we conduct a runtime configuration

Figure 55: The Home Depot. The selected store location is lost after the restart.

Figure 57: Uber Driver. The numeric content in the phone number box is lost after the restart.

Figure 56: TacoBell. The number in the ZIP code box is lost after the restart.

Figure 58: Booking.com. The textual content in the destination search box is lost after the restart.

change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to CC FileManager. After the restart, the opened Storage page is reset to the home page. The opened directory is also lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 59.

- 94. **Speed Booster.** First, we conduct a boost, which is finished with a boost report page. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Speed Booster. After the restart, the boost report page is reset. The boost point is also reset. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 60.
- 95. **Firefox.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Firefox.
- 96. **Twitch.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Twitch.

- 97. **Target.** First, we uncheck the "Keep me signed in" option. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Target. After the restart, the "Keep me signed in" option is reset to the checked state. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 61.
- 98. **Smart Booster.** First, we conduct a storage scan, which is finished with a storage report page. Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart to Smart Booster. After the restart, the list of specific storage situations is lost. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 62.
- 99. **Bumble.** First, we populate the country search box with the textual content. The candidate countries change based on their similarity to the textual content.

Figure 59: CC FileManager. After the restart, the opened Storage page is reset to the home page. The opened directory is also lost.

Figure 60: Speed Booster. After the restart, the boost report page is reset. The boost point is also reset.

Then, we conduct a runtime configuration change. The runtime configuration change causes a restart of Bumble. After the restart, the candidate countries are reset to the default countries. The experimental result is shown in Fig. 63.

100. **Wish.** We do not find a runtime change issue with Wish.

Figure 61: Target. The unchecked "Keep me signed in" option is reset to the checked state after the restart.

Figure 62: Smart Booster. The list of specific storage situations is lost after the restart.

Figure 63: Bumble. The candidate countries are reset to the default countries after the restart.